

Ernest Hemingway's ideology about War, And Feminism

Jarnail Singh, Research Scholar, PhD English

NIILM University, Kaithal, Haryana

History has a record a number of wars in the world. War creates history. War is a symbol of power. Everyone wants to become powerful. War leads destruction, death, suffering. It kills innocent people also. The world has seen great war World War I, World War II. When it comes to American literature regarding World War I, A Farewell to Arms is unrivalled. The topic of this is Ernest Hemingway's ideology towards War and Feminism. It is an important in understanding Hemingway's concept of war and women. Woman is an important person of society. Feminism plays a great role in the world. Feminism believes in equality of women. Hemingway's women are very powerful. A Farewell to Arms and For Whom the Bell Tolls are powerful American novel. The narrative is largely driven by the threat of war. According to Samue Shaw, "as a war novel, that is its depiction of man in battle, A Farewell to Arms belongs with the supreme example of the genre." It is worth noting that Maxwell Perkins, Hemingway's editor, had his doubts about A Farewell to Arms' suitability as a war novel. However, Owen Wister read the novel as a romantic tale. "An improbable hero and heroine live in adolescent dream life," as Robert Lewis puts it, makes for a "wildly romantic" story. It marked Hemingway's arrival on the literary scene as a major personality. In a sense, A Farewell to Arms acted "as the great alibi for a generation." Since Hemingway referred to it as "his Romeo and Juliet" novel, it is fair to assume that the novel is romantic in tone.

The Portrayal of War and Violence in Hemingway's Fiction" is to analyse the author's portrayal of war and its attendant brutality in his three most famous works: The Sun Also Rises, For Whom the Bell Tolls, and A Farewell to Arms. The literary world was profoundly affected by the war. Since 3600 B.C human race has been afflicted with nearly 15000 wars which brought death to 4 million people, a part from it, millions of

people were wounded and many billions were died in famine and pestilence that follow in the wake of war, How many young poets, scientists, artists, inventors, novelists, dramatists, musicians, physicians and professor were lost to the world no exception to it. Hemingway served in both World Wars, from 1939 to 1945. He served in World War I (1914-18) and the Spanish Civil War (1936-1939). From the early stories and sketches, primarily from *In Our Time*, to *A Farewell to Arms*, and finally *For Whom the Bell Tolls*, the works between 1923 and 1940 attempt to interstate his shifting attitudes towards war.

His female protagonists are all good, submissive and docile. An examination of Hemingway's Novels reveal that" most of his female protagonists like Catherine, Maria, Brett confront an different experiences even in hostile environment. But some critics find fault of Hemingway in the portrayal of Women. Feminist criticism has ridiculed Hemingway's Women more "passive", women as sexual pawns for Hemingway's heroes. In 1950 Theodore Bardacke said that the little " has been said of Hemingway's heroines beyond an acknowledgement of an antagonism towards women". 1 (Bardacke, 307) Philip Young generalizes that the women " are either vicious, destructive wives like Macomber's, or day dreams like Catherine, Maria and Renata". 2 (Young,81) I have selected Hemingway's popular novels *The Sun Also Rises*, *A Farewell to Arms*, *To Have and Have Not*, *Across the River and Into the Trees* and *For Whom the Bell Tolls*. These novels are feministic. Hemingway has created most popular female characters in these novels. Critic has agreed that Hemingway's works particularly *The Sun Also Rises*, *A Farewell to Arms*, *To Have and Have Not*, *Across the River and Into the Trees* and *For Whom the Bell Tolls* show Ernest Hemingway as a Feminist. His female characters are helpful and co-operative. His female protagonists are all good, submissive and docile. An examination of Hemingway's Novels reveal that" most of his female protagonists like Catherine, Maria, Brett confront an different experiences even in hostile environment. Main focus of my research has been to make a systematic study of Hemingway's selected novels and to show that he is war novelist and his female characters are best. He has depicted hunting, boxing, bullfighting and fishing in his works but we misunderstand his depictions of different women in his novels.

Hemingway's novels and his own life also make readers to think that he was indifferent to women and had "growing antagonism"³ (Scott, 2000) towards them. But this is not right. The critics simply divided his fictional women into either bitches or helpmates, either demons or angels. A careful study shows that Hemingway vividly created different types of women with depth and strength in his novels. While analyzing the women characters in Hemingway's Novels, he divides them : traditional women, new women and ideal women. Traditional women are shown in stories "Cat in the Rain", "Indian Camp", and "The Doctors and The Doctors Wife". And second type or new women are in his famous novels Brett Ashley in *The Sun Also Rises*(1926) and Margot Macomber in *The Short Happy Life of Francis Macomber* and Catherine Byrne in *The Garden of Eden*. Hemingway's ideal women are Catherine Barkley in *A Farewell to Arms*(1929) and Maria in *For Whom the Bell Tolls*(1940).

Feminist or feminism is about all genders having equal rights and opportunities for women. It is about respecting diverse women's experiences, identities, knowledge and strengths. Feminism is the belief that women should have the same rights and opportunities as men. It is to empower all women to realise their full rights and strengths. Feminism is the belief that women deserve equal social, economic, political rights and freedom. Feminism has also explored racism, gender norms, and self expression. Feminism goes beyond basic rights and has deeper cultural shifts to sexism and intersectional oppression based on gender, race, sexuality and class.

A Farewell to Arms is a classic work in American fiction. It is about World War I. Samuel Shaw writes: "As a war novel, that is its depiction of man in battle *A Farewell to Arms* belongs to the supreme example of Genre." Samuel Shaw (1973:53). However, Hemingway's editor, Maxwell Perkins had reservations about *A Farewell to Arms* as a war novel. It was considered more an autobiographical novel. Hemingway based *A Farewell to Arms* partly on his personal experience as a Red Cross ambulance driver in 1918. The horror of *A Farewell to Arms* comes full circle when it is shown how the officers in the army are shot down. Frederic Henry, finding no meaning in such senseless brutality, is completely disillusioned and runs away from the line. The same situation is faced Nick when he meets the killers.

"It's hell of a thing".

War is very dangerous. In war women also play a major role. Catherine Barkley plays the role of a nurse in *A Farewell to Arms*. She helps the wounded soldiers.

The fear of death separates the coward from the brave. When Catherine amends Henry's quotation that "the coward dies a thousand deaths, the brave but one," by saying that "the brave dies perhaps two thousands deaths if he's intelligent. He simply doesn't mention them," Henry admits that he is not brave and says: "I don't know. It's hard to see inside the head of the brave." Whether or not Hemingway came to see inside the head of the brave, he held the fear of death as the ultimate test of manhood. The meaning of his African story, "The Short Happy Life of Francis Macomber" depends much on this fear of death.

Hemingway's women characters are differently delineated in his novels. Their traits are also different. Some women characters are meek, womanly in their behaviour, while some are villain-like figures. Some heroines are like Bitches. In the delineation of woman, Hemingway was dictated by what happened when war ceased followed by disillusionment in true love. The unfavourable portrait of Mrs. Macomber who killed her husband for having obstructed in her affairs with a guide is simple, an illustration of the frustration which the novelist experienced in his times.

Hemingway's Experience of War : Knowledge, according to Hemingway, was essential to the author if he was to make his reader know too, if the author was to convey a sense of immediacy and reality in his writing. An experience of war, he said, was a great advantage to a writer because it was "one of the major subjects and certainly one of the hardest to write truly of." Those writers who had not seen war were always very jealous and tried to make it seem unimportant, or abnormal, or a disease as a subject, while really it was just something quite irreplaceable that they had missed. Hemingway's own participation in two world wars enabled him to give literary reality to one of the major experiences of his generation and the generation that followed. The tragic destruction of innocence in *A Farewell to Arms*, and the richer, deeper exploration of Robert Jordan's mature and sophisticated mind in *For Whom the Bell*

Tolls certainly make them two of the most representative novels of the times to which they belong.

The Hero and the Code Hero in "A Farewell to Arms" (1929)

A Farewell to Arms has Frederic Henry as the hero. Henry is wounded in the war as was Nick Adams (although now the most serious of his injuries is to his knee, which is where Hemingway himself was wounded in World War I). Henry shows clearly the results of this misfortune; again he cannot sleep at night unless he stops thinking; again, when he does sleep he has nightmares. The nearest approach to the code hero in this novel is the priest who tells Henry what is meant by true love and who finds comfort in his religious faith and in natural scenery the code.

"A Farewell to Arms" (1929) is a complex novel. It is a war story. In A Farewell to Arms, Frederic Henry, a lieutenant with an ambulance unit serving the Italian army in World War I, lives with stoical matter-of-factness through the ennui of a stabilized war-front and the overwhelming debacle after the Austro-German break-through at Caporetto. From all this, even from the awareness of all this, he escapes into his love-affair with the English nurse Catherine Barkley. He escapes, that is, into a world where the essential needs of a man for amusement, food, companionship, love, and spiritual wholeness-may be satisfied with decency and even with a certain grace. As with *The Sun Also Rises*, the appeal of the book is complex; it interests not only by its love story, but also by its passages of swiftly paced action, by its expression of the mood of overwhelming revulsion against war which lasted into the nineteen-thirties, and by the overwhelming actuality of its chapters on the rout of the Italian army.

A Great War Novel :

In writing A Farewell to Arms Hemingway went back to the war to see if what happened to his generation in it was responsible for their being "lost" in the 1920's. For many this is the great novel of World War I, though the largest novel in American literature. *The Bull-Fighter*, a Man with the Code Hemingway is much influenced by bull fighting, *the Sun Also Rises* is about bull fighting.

Hemingway's next two books were works of non-fiction. The books are *Death in the Afternoon* and *The Green Hills of Africa*. The first is a book about *The Sun Also Rises*.

To conclude Hemingway is a powerful war novelist. His women are superb and good. His female Catherine, Maria and Brett are well portrayed. They are good for the men whom they are involved. Hemingway is a powerful American war novelist. His women are superb. Their role is very important during war time. Catherine is a good nurse. Maria brings comfort and peace in Jordan's life. Hemingway's women are fantastic, good.

Work Cited:

1. Theodore, Bardacke. "Hemingway's Women", Ernest Hemingway: The Man and His Work. ed MC Caffery, John K.M. New York, Avon.1950
2. Philip Young, Ernest Hemingway, Pennsylvania State University Press,1966. p.81
3. Hemingway, Ernest. *The Old Man and the Sea* 1952. New York, Charles Scribner's Sons,1952.